

Gold

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This is not the green
I was taught to call beautiful.

The grass has let go
of its chlorophyll—
gone blonde, gone pale,
gone the colour of patience
stretched thin across the paddock,
and still it holds.

The trees stand alone,
dark green and stubborn,
scattered across the gold
like words
in a sentence
that doesn't need
to say much,
that breathes in silence
and leaves room
for everything else.

Underneath, the earth brown waits—
I cannot see it,
but I feel it:
roots drinking in quiet,
water weaving below,
life moving unseen,
holding the memory of rain,
holding
what the eye cannot reach.

The wind passes,
whispering through blades,
light bends along them,

a slow pulse
I can neither name nor claim,
and I move through it
and it moves through me,
and something opens
where I did not know a self existed.

This is not the beauty
that begs to be seen.
It does not shimmer.
It does not sing.
It just stays—
dry and wide,
impossible to forget,
asking nothing,
offering
a different way to exist,
a way to receive without knowing,
to be shaped without intention,
to hold and be held
by what does not intend
to teach
and yet teaches everything.

Note on Connected Outputs

This poem is a companion piece to the essay “What Does It Mean to Be Taught by the Nonhuman?” (Ocriciano, 2026), published in *Educational Philosophy and Theory* as part of the collective essay “Educational Posthumanism at the Limits of Modern Humanism.” The poem and essay are connected outputs: the essay argues philosophically for a circulation between intentional teaching and nonhuman availability; the poem enacts that circulation. They are different forms of the same inquiry.

Related output

Ocriciano, M. (2026). What does it mean to be taught by the nonhuman? In M. Okabe et al., *Educational posthumanism at the limits of modern humanism: Logos, pathos, and the circulation between humanism and posthumanism*. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*.